

Comment on “Atomic transport coefficients of liquid $3d$ transition metals: insights from local field corrections” [Appl. Phys. A **131**, 828 (2025)]

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In a recent paper, Romman *et al.* [1] studied atomic transport coefficients of liquid $3d$ transition metals using the Bretonnet–Silbert (BS) pseudopotential with five local-field correction functions (LFCFs), including Ichimaru–Utsumi (IU) [2] and Farid *et al.* (F) [3]. A central finding of Ref. [1] is that the Farid LFCF produces a substantially deeper potential well than the other four LFCFs (see Fig. 1 of Ref. [1]), with the authors stating that “the depth of the potential well is maximum for F-LFCF for all systems examined.” The purpose of this Comment is to point out that this result is inconsistent with the known properties of the Farid LFCF and likely originates from an error in the numerical implementation.

The Farid LFCF, $G_{\text{pr}}(q)$, was derived by Farid *et al.* [3] as an improvement over the IU model $G_{\text{UI}}(q)$. Both share the same analytic structure [Eqs. (15a) and (31a) of Ref. [3]], which differ only in their coefficients. Crucially, as shown in Fig. 8 of Ref. [3], the two functions are nearly identical for metallic densities ($r_s \approx 2-3$). The difference $G_{\text{pr}}(q) - G_{\text{UI}}(q)$ is small and concentrated near $q = 2q_F$. Since the effective pair potential is obtained by integrating over q , a small localized difference in $G(q)$ can only produce a correspondingly small changes in pair potential.

To verify this quantitatively, we have independently implemented both LFCFs following the original formulas of Ref. [3] and computed the effective pair potentials for the same metals and BS parameters as in Ref. [1]. Figure 1 shows the results. Panel (a) compares $G_{\text{UI}}(q)$ (solid purple) and $G_{\text{pr}}(q)$ (yellow circles) at $r_s = 2.5$, where $r_s = (3/4\pi Z_s n)^{1/3}$ is the electron-density parameter in Hartree atomic units [2]. This

value is close to those for Cu, Cr, and Fe ($r_s \approx 2.48$ – 2.51 for $Z_s = 1.4$ and $n \approx 0.073$ – 0.076 \AA^{-3} in Ref. [1]). This confirms that the two LFCFs were nearly indistinguishable. Panel (b) shows the difference: $G_F - G_{IU}$ (yellow circles) remains small across the entire q range. Panels (c) and (d) show the resulting pair potentials for liquid Sc and Cu, respectively. For direct comparison, the F curves from Fig. 1 (a)(b) of Ref. [1] were digitized and overlaid (solid yellow lines). The IU and correct Farid curves (yellow circles) overlapped almost perfectly, with well depths agreeing within 1%. Yet the digitized F curve of Ref. [1] shows anomalously deep wells, far exceeding both.

The anomalously deep Farid well reported in Ref. [1] therefore points to an error in the implementation of the Farid LFCF coefficients. The Farid LFCF involves four density-dependent coefficients (A, B, C, D) given by Eqs. (31b)–(31e) of Ref. [3], which in turn depend on several intermediate quantities ($b_0^A, b_0^B, b_0^C, b_{-2}, \gamma_0, \delta_2, \delta_4$). Since the source code is not available, we cannot identify the precise origin of the discrepancy. However, we have verified that a misplacement of the $-16b_{-2}$ term in Eq. (31b) of Ref. [3]—placing it outside the $\frac{15}{4096}$ bracket—yields a dramatically different A coefficient ($A \approx -0.7$ instead of $A \approx 0.029$) and produces anomalous pair potentials. The curve labeled F* in Figure 1 (red dashed in all panels) was computed with this bracket error. As shown in panels (a) and (b), the resulting $G_{F^*}(q)$ deviates strongly from $G_{IU}(q)$ for $q \gtrsim q_F$, with the difference exceeding -5 . The resulting pair potentials [panels (c) and (d)] reproduce the qualitative behavior reported in Ref. [1]. Such a bracket error has been noted in at least one secondary source [4] that presents the Farid coefficients in a rearranged form. We note that a similar anomaly appears in a subsequent paper by Das and Gosh [5] from the same group, which employs the same set of LFCFs.

In conclusion, the Farid LFCF, when correctly implemented, gives pair potentials that are nearly identical to those from the IU LFCF. The large differences reported in Ref. [1] and Ref. [5] are artifacts of an implementation error, and the transport coefficients derived from the erroneous Farid potential should be reconsidered.

Code availability

The source code (Julia) for reproducing Figure 1 is available as a Jupyter notebook at https://colab.research.google.com/gist/hsugawa8651/b057ed3b99d110019585979147bd1cad/comment.fig1_supplementary.ipynb.

References

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Fig. 1 (a) Local-field correction functions $G(q)$ at $r_s = 2.5$ (similar to Cu, Cr, and Fe in Ref. [1]): IU (solid purple), correct Farid (yellow circles), and F^* (erroneous bracket, red dashed). (b) Difference from IU: $G_F - G_{IU}$ (yellow circles) and $G_{F^*} - G_{IU}$ (red dashed). (c,d) Effective pair potentials for liquid Sc and Cu. Solid yellow line: F curves digitized from Fig. 1 (a)(b) of Ref. [1]; yellow circles: F computed with the correct Farid LFCF, overlapping with IU; red dashed: F^* (bracket error); solid purple: IU. All calculated using the BS parameters from Ref. [1]. In all panels, the IU and correct Farid curves are nearly indistinguishable, while the F curve of Ref. [1] shows an anomalously deep well.